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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, VII.

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1. Introduction

As outlined in the overview given at the INCA colloquium in Sitges, Jan 1988 (S. Söderhjelm: 'Double star processing by NDAC'), the known multiple stars will be processed by the STDMUL program. Preliminary multiple-star solutions were previously reported in NDAC/LO/080, but a more realistic STDMUL has now been written along the same lines as STDDBL (and similarly lacking most of the I/O-parts). Because multiple stars may have so many different arrangements in the number, positions and magnitudes of the components, exhaustive tests of STDMUL covering a large portion of this parameter-space are impossible. Instead, I have considered only rather 'difficult' quintuple systems, expecting any problems to show up more clearly. Due to the limits of computer-power available, even these partial tests are less comprehensive than I would have liked. The computing-times grow rapidly with the number of components, and the present simulations have consumed rather more than 1500 CPU-hours on the Lund HP 9000.

2. Key points of STDMUL

In its main structure, the STDMUL program is very similar to STDDBL, but there are of course important changes in the details. Firstly, with n_c components, there are generally $6n_c + 1$ solution parameters (the extra one for the IFOV-profile scale-factor). As in STDDBL, $x(1)$ - $x(6)$ are the magnitude and the astrometric parameters for the primary, while $x(7)$ - $x(6n_c)$ give data relative to the primary. Secondly, the number of Input Catalogue entries (=IFOV-pointings) is specified by a variable n_p , which may take values from 1 to n_c for different multiples. The nominal position-offsets (relative to the reference point) are also needed for each pointing. The calculation of differential coefficients is straightforward, but for the IFOV scale-factor, the slope of the IFOV-profile has to be calculated at each component and each pointing. The weighting-corrections due to the effective pointing-variance are similarly more complicated, but no new principles are involved.

In this way, the main part of STDMUL has been completed, consisting (as STDDBL) of a first mesh-search for the primary position, using the *a priori* relative positions, and then a final unconstrained least squares solution. For the present testing purposes, the interesting output is a comparison of the solution parameters with the 'known' (simulated) ones. As before, I use the straight rms astrometric error (5 parameters) for each component as a measure of the goodness of the solution. Similarly important are the S_e -values (squared sum of the actual over the formal error for the five astrometric parameters), which

should ideally be χ^2 -distributed with 5 degrees of freedom.

3. The simulated quintuples

The double star simulation-program, including the derivation of Case History Files, was modified to give data for multiples with $n_c=5$. The detailed separations and magnitude differences in the systems do of course determine the accuracies obtained, but instead of investigating these dependencies, it was thought more important to test different IFOV pointing-strategies. Therefore, three sets of 'typical' quintuples were simulated, with only the position angles and the position on the sky as variables. (To reduce the scatter, all systems were put at ecliptic latitude plus or minus 30 degrees).

The simplest case is a 'trapezium'-configuration, with all five components within a small area, and a single IFOV-pointing at the photocentre. This Ser. A has a central double (1 arcsec separation) accompanied by a second one 5 arcsec away, and with a fifth single component at 5 arcsec in another direction. One hundred such systems were simulated, with H-magnitudes fixed at (8.5+10.0), (10.0+11.5) and 11.5 for the 5 components. The primary position was given a single-coordinate gaussian $\sigma=1$ arcsec, and the relative positions had $\sigma=0.1$ or 0.2 arcsec.

In Ser. B (100 systems), the same general topology and magnitudes were kept, but now the second binary was at 20 arcsec from the first one. This necessitates two IFOV-pointings, the first at the photocentre of components 1,2 and 5, the second one at the second double (components 3 and 4).

For the 100 runs of Ser. C, finally, the second double and the fifth component are each at 15 arcsec from the central double, with three separate IFOV-pointings. In the present version of the simulation program, the total observing-time (4 slots, out of 20) can not be divided equally between three pointings. The faint single star was given the larger part, in the division 1,1,2.

Later, smaller series A1,B1 and C1 (25 systems each) were run, where all the components had the same (H=8.5) magnitude. In Ser. C1, the total observing time is 3 slots (instead of 4), equally divided between the pointings.

4. Astrometric solution results

In the first part of the solutions, the position of the primary component is found by constraining the relative data and then varying the position of the primary in a circular search-mesh (cf. NDAC/LO/107). No extensive trials with different $C\chi_a$ -limits and mesh-sizes have been made, but in the course of the solutions, some changes from obviously poor parameters were made. For $n_p=1$, the 'standard' double star values $C\chi_a=50$, $g=0.7$ arcsec worked well. For $n_p=2$, $C\chi_a=50$ was definitely too high, giving an excessive number of false positions later rejected by the 'final' solutions. Again, the standard double star value $C\chi_a=25$ was more suitable. (For quintuples, the computing time required for a final solution is an order of magnitude greater than for each preliminary mesh-solution, making a large $C\chi_a$ very uneconomical). For $n_p=3$, even $C\chi_a=25$ proved too high, and here $C\chi_a=10$ gave better results.

In the mean, some 15-20 mesh-points have to be tried before the final unconstrained least-squares solution can be made. Roughly, the total computing

time for one solution is then about n_p hours, scaling somewhat like $n_p n_c^2$ (?). Often, the final solution does converge to parameters close to the real ones. For a non-negligible proportion of systems, however, the solution for one or more of the fainter stars is poor, even when the final fit to the observations S_f is satisfactorily low. Especially the faint component in the second double (component 4, $H=11.5$) is liable to this problem.

Judging by the results of earlier multiple-star experiments, a likely reason for faulty solutions is a too large *a priori* error in the relative positions. Looking at the successful solutions (defined by $(S_e)_{max} < 45$), one may give limits in the maximum (over the 4 secondary components) position error relative to the primary such that all solutions are good. For Ser. A, this limit is 0.32 arcsec, for Ser. B it is 0.17 arcsec, and for Ser. C 0.13 arcsec. Only if we know all the relative positions in the object to better than this accuracy can we be sure that STD MUL will give a correct solution. The mean rms-errors for these solutions are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Mean astrometric errors (mas) for the five components for n runs with small relative *a priori* errors. The estimated mean errors of these means are given in parentheses.

Ser.	n	rms1	rms2	rms3	rms4	rms5
A($n_p=1$)	66	1.4(0.1)	4.7(0.3)	4.6(0.2)	24(5)	21(1)
B($n_p=2$)	20	1.4(0.1)	4.9(0.4)	8.1(0.9)	31(4)	23(2)
C($n_p=3$)	13	1.8(0.2)	6.6(0.6)	8.2(1.4)	39(6)	26(3)

Clearly, it is easier to get a good solution, and the astrometric errors are smaller, for a 'trapezium-type' multiple with a single IFOV-pointing. The sensitivity to the *a priori* errors, and the actual errors of the solution, both increase with an increasing number of IFOV-pointings.

Although the faint components (4 and 5) may be misplaced if the *a priori* errors are too large, the first three components are *not* much affected. This can be seen in Table 2, where the straight mean astrometric errors are given for all converged solutions. (For about 3 systems out of 100, no solution at all was obtained, mostly because of *a priori* errors larger than 0.50 arcsec).

Table 2. Mean astrometric errors (mas) for the five components for all the n converged runs in each series. The estimated mean errors of these means are given in parentheses.

Ser.	n	rms1	rms2	rms3	rms4	rms5
A($n_p=1$)	96	1.5(0.1)	5.2(0.3)	5.6(0.4)	55(14)	22(1)
B($n_p=2$)	97	1.5(0.1)	5.6(0.3)	8.1(0.4)	128(25)	45(11)
C($n_p=3$)	98	1.8(0.1)	6.7(0.3)	10.2(0.5)	244(42)	43(18)

The figures in Tables 1 and 2 may be compared with the data for doubles given in Table 3. Typically, a component in a quintuple will have its astrometric errors determined with about 50% larger mean errors than an equally bright component in a double system. This is no serious degradation, and it is partly reflected in the mean errors as obtained from the inverse normal equations matrix. As shown in Table 4, The S_e -values are close to 8 (except for the problem component 4), indicating that a 25 % increase in the formal mean errors is sufficient.

Table 3. Mean astrometric errors (mas) for double star components at different magnitudes and separations. The primary has $H=8.5$, and secondaries at $H=10.0$ and 11.5 are considered. The data are means over all ecliptic latitudes and over ranges in separation and magnitude-difference, but they should be accurate within the mean errors given in parentheses.

Sep	rms(pr)	rms(10.0)	rms(11.5)
1" ($n_p=1$)	1.0(0.1)	3.4(0.3)	12(2)
20" ($n_p=2$)	1.1(0.1)	5.0(0.5)	19(3)

Table 4. Mean S_e -values for the five components for all the n converged runs in each series. The estimated mean errors of these means are given in parentheses. (Actually, S_{e2} - S_{e5} are for the astrometric parameters relative to the primary).

Ser.	n	Se1	Se2	Se3	Se4	Se5
A($n_p=1$)	96	9(1)	8(1)	11(2)	160(80)	9(2)
B($n_p=2$)	97	7(1)	7(1)	7(1)	70(20)	40(20)
C($n_p=3$)	98	7(1)	7(1)	10(1)	160(40)	8(2)

So far, all the tested systems have a dominating primary component. It was thought interesting also to see some results for systems with equal components. Only the 3x25 runs in Ser. A1-C1 are available, but it is at once apparent that more solutions completely fail to converge (2 out of 25 for $n_p=1$, 4 out of 25 for $n_p=2$ and 3). The statistics are poor, but all of these failures had *a priori* errors greater than 0.19 arcsec, showing again that 0.15 arcsec in the relative positions is a 'safe' limit. Further, all the converged solutions are 'true', because it is now impossible to have a reasonable fit to the observations unless all the (equally bright) components are correctly placed.

Because all the components have the same magnitude, we may combine their rms-deviations and S_e -values to a single mean for each n_p , as done in Table 5. For components in double systems, the corresponding rms-errors are about 1.3 mas at 1 arcsec separation and 1.8 mas at 20 arcsec, thus the error-increase from double to quintuple is now almost a factor 2. This is a bit more than expected, but such equal-magnitude systems are in practice very rare. (Heuristically, the 'effective amplitude' for each component, relative to the 'DC' background of the other components scales as n_c^{-1} , and the phase-error would then scale as $n_c^{0.5}$).

Table 5. Mean astrometric errors (mas) and S_e -values for equal ($H=8.5$) components in quintuple systems. (The rms-value for the C1 series has been multiplied by 0.87 to compensate for the 25 % shorter observing time).

Ser	n	rms	Se
A1 ($n_p=1$)	115	2.5(0.1)	5.4(0.4)
B1 ($n_p=2$)	105	3.0(0.1)	4.0(0.3)
C1 ($n_p=3$)	100	3.4(0.2)	5.4(0.4)

5. Photometric results

Finally, we have to check also the photometric results. With guidance from the double star results, all magnitudes were first corrected for the expected colour-equations (eq. (1) in NDAC/LO/110, $d(dm)$ with same 0.082-slope).

After these corrections, straight means of the (sol-true)-values were formed for all 'good' solutions ($(S_e)_{max} < 30$, and sol-true < 1 magnitude), as reported in Table 6.

Table 6. Mean photometric errors (sol-true, in thousandths of a magnitude) for the different components of the standard quintuple systems. Only 'good' solutions are included, and in parenthesis are given first the actual standard deviations, then the ones computed from the inverse normal equations matrix.

Ser	n	pr	(2-pr)	(3-pr)	(4-pr)	(5-pr)
A ($n_p=1$)	85	-2(6/4)	+1(17/17)	+2(17/18)	+10(73/ 72)	-14(70/ 63)
B ($n_p=2$)	76	-10(7/5)	-3(21/19)	-33(41/32)	-27(156/124)	+6(76/ 74)
C ($n_p=3$)	63	-24(8/6)	+8(29/23)	-31(45/32)	-43(111/129)	+14(117/110)

The data for $n_p=1$ look very satisfactory, with virtually no systematic shifts, and with standard deviations close to the expectations. For $n_p=2$ and 3, however, the results are less clearcut. There is now a constant offset in the primary star magnitudes, and also the components of the second binary come out too bright. The systematic offsets are *not* colour-dependent, and the fixed simulation parameters preclude an empirical search for a dependence on magnitudes and/or separations. The spread around the offsets are quite reasonable, however, as can be seen from the similarity of the two values within each parenthesis.

A similar study for the equal-magnitude systems is summarized in Table 7. Here, as expected, there are no effects in the relative data, *but* all components show exactly the same deviation (increasing with n_p) as in the 'unequal' case. Further study is needed to explain the effect, which is however too small to be considered a major problem.

Table 7. Mean photometric errors (sol-true, in thousandths of a magnitude) for the different components of the equal-magnitude quintuples. In parenthesis are given first the actual standard deviations, then the ones computed from the inverse normal equations matrix. The mean column gives the mean deviation for all components.

Ser	n	Comp 1	(2-1)	(3-1)	(4-1)	(5-1)	mean
A1 ($n_p=1$)	23	-1(10/10)	+5(12/13)	+4(12/14)	+4(12/13)	+5(13/14)	+3
B1 ($n_p=2$)	21	-9(11/13)	+6(18/17)	-6(15/19)	-6(19/19)	+1(16/19)	-10
C1 ($n_p=3$)	20	-30(19/16)	+2(20/20)	+2(24/21)	+4(25/21)	-2(20/21)	-29

6. Conclusions

The main parts of 'STDMUL' are now working, and after the present tests, we may conclude the following:

1. In a majority of cases, the program works even for rather difficult quintuple systems. For the more frequent triples and quadruples, there should be no major problems.
2. The problems encountered in the present tests are mostly due to the large magnitude-difference between the faintest components and the sum of the brighter ones. (With magnitudes $m, m+1.5, m+1.5, m+3, m+3$, this effective magnitude-difference is about 3.5). Even when the solution fails for the

faint components, the brighter ones have their parameters determined with full accuracy.

3. A knowledge of the *a priori* relative errors to within 0.15 arcsec gives a high probability of solution success for all reasonable quintuples. For doubles, this limit is more like 0.3–0.4 arcsec, and for triples and quadruples, intermediate values seem likely.
4. The real astrometric errors are usually not more than 20-30% above the formal ones given by the inverse normal equations matrix.
5. The photometric data show random errors of the expected magnitude, but there are some systematic effects present that can not be simply explained. Further investigations should be done, but they are presently postponed.

As for STDDBL, the Input/Output parts of STD MUL are lacking. The work will now concentrate on SEEKDBL, and only when all three of the 'major' double-star reduction programs have been shown to work will these questions be taken up in more detail.